

IMPROVING MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS TO STUDY ENGLISH

Nafisa Jabborova Hikmatovna

English Teacher of Languages Department of Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers Bukhara Branch, Uzbekistan, Bukhara

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Abstract:

This article discusses the main ways and types of increasing the motivation of students of non-linguistic specialties in the process of learning English. The article also poses tasks and analyzes methodological paths and pedagogical approaches to increase interest in the subject among students. The relevance of the study lies in the fact that motivation is the most important beginning of the process of mastering a foreign language, which is directly related to the effectiveness of training.

Key Words: Motivation, Educational Motivation, Foreign Language, Improvement, Student, Information Technology

Improving Motivation of Students to Study English:

“Knowledge only becomes knowledge when it is acquired by the efforts of one’s thought, and not by memory.” L.N. Tolstoy

Today, English is the language of international communication. An important reason for learning any foreign language is that new opportunities are opening up before us. Speaking a foreign language, we can improve the quality of our life in all its fields, it helps to broaden our horizons, allows us to learn the culture and customs of another people, and helps us to be successful and prosperous in business.

Practical experience convinces us that the most important thing in teaching a foreign language is the motivation of students. Proper motivation is half the success.

Engineering students usually do not have a motivation to learn a language during the training period, and the possible prospects for its use in their professional future activities are not yet clear to them. Such students are primarily focused on specialty disciplines, as they have a technical mentality and it is difficult for them to get foreign languages and humanitarian subjects. Therefore, students do not attach much importance to the language, putting it last. But already in advanced courses, English becomes a means of mastering experience and advanced knowledge, a necessary tool for professional development and a way to prepare themselves for a career. To solve this problem, at the moment, teachers of higher educational institutions use in their practice a huge number of techniques and methods for improving a foreign language, including the formation of students' motivation to learn it.

According to the definition of I.A. Zimnyaya [Зимняя И.А, р. 130–134.], “A motive is what determines, stimulates, induces a person to perform some action, included in the activity defined by this motive”. Educational and cognitive motivation of students is their active approach to learning, the realization of the desire to study well. Any cognitive activity includes knowledge, skills and motivational components, such as motive, interest and attitude. The question of motivation at the beginning stage of education is very important, as the foundations for children to be able and willing to learn are laid in primary school age. Motive itself is the source of activity and performs the function of impulse and word formation. [Markova A.K. 1990; - p. 192].

Students can be encouraged to learn a foreign language in different ways, the teacher must imagine the whole range of motivational tools and techniques to achieve the main goal of teaching a foreign language.

The method of project activity in English lessons is a way to increase motivation to learn the language and the opportunity to show creative abilities, independence of the idea, as well as put the knowledge into practice. The project task that should be done by student directly connects the process of mastering the language with the ability of real use of this knowledge. Thus, the orientation towards creating a project as a personal educational product makes the process of mastering subject knowledge personally important for each student, personally motivated. The relevance of this methodological development lies in the fact that due to the rapid change in the requirements for students' learning, the project is a new modern educational technology that allows solving problems personally, that is, an oriented approach to learning and meeting the needs of modern society.

This technique allows students to develop:

- communicative, creative, intellectual skills;
- the culture of their communication;
- the ability to formulate their own thoughts;
- the ability to tolerate the opinion of communication partners;

- the ability to extract and process any information, as well as navigate in the information space;
- develop skills in using modern computer technologies;
- language communication, on the basis of which there is a natural need for a foreign language;
- apply the accumulated knowledge of the subject;
- critical and creative communication.

Using ICTs to enhance student motivation in English classes. To interest students in learning foreign languages, it is necessary to organize the educational process so that it causes high motivation and ensures their activity in the lesson. Today it is necessary to keep pace with the times. Therefore, a modern lesson should be progressive, interesting, informative and creative. And for this we need a great desire, a creative approach, and knowledge of information technology, faith in ourselves and in our smart and curious students. The use of information technology, for example, in combination with the project method allows students apply their knowledge, skills, and abilities practically and therefore it is one of the forms of organizing research and cognitive activity, in which collective activity is successfully implemented, which allows increase motivation in learning foreign languages. Usually, the student himself stands in the center of attention of such a work process with the possibility of free expression of his opinion. Students find practical application of knowledge for foreign language speech when creating presentations on various topics. Using my personal experience, I can say that such an organization of educational activity gives each student the opportunity to express themselves, show their skills, knowledge and abilities, and at the same time get a positive assessment. Modern education sets certain goals and objectives, the solution of which changes approaches to the organization of work: the emphasis is transferred from the assimilation of knowledge to the formation of competence. There occurs the reorientation to the individual - oriented approach. Educational institutions are provided with modern computers, electronic resources with access to the Internet. Such factors contribute the usage of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

The use of computer programs in the process of teaching English does not interfere with the solution of the communicative problem, but rather increases its effectiveness, since the teacher can build a lesson that could most effectively achieve the educational goal. In my opinion, it is better to demonstrate a small fragment than to show a fully educational video film designed for a whole lesson. The teacher can produce different material according to his desire, using several computer educational programs, and calculating time accuracy according to the abilities of a particular group and each student individually. Modern multimedia material allows you to display a specific passage or some task on the big screen, use the necessary video plot or audio in an English lesson using a projector.

Thus, the creative approach allows the teacher use a very important tool as a computer in his work very effectively represented by modern computer educational technologies.

Music is one of the best ways to touch the feelings and emotions of students. The song gives a great surge of enthusiasm and is a pleasant and stimulating approach to the study of the culture of foreign countries. Unlike grammar structures, which disappear from the head at the end of the lesson, good songs are not forgotten. Songs can live long and become part of someone's culture. The methodological advantages of songs in teaching English are as follows:

- songs are a means of more solid assimilation and expansion of the lexical stock, because they include new words and expressions;
- in songs, already familiar vocabulary is found in a new contextual environment, which helps to activate it. The songs often contain proper names, geographical names, realities of the studied country language, poetic words. This increases the development of students' sense of language, knowledge of its stylistic features;
- grammar constructions are better absorbed and activated in songs;
- songs help to improve pronunciation skills. Songs help to relax, take a short break in the routine of educational activities in the lesson.

Extracurricular activities. This type of activity helps students to overcome difficulties in learning and in asserting themselves, as it allows students to reveal their capabilities and abilities. Extracurricular activities expand the space in which students can develop their creative and cognitive activity, realize their best personal qualities, which often remain unclaimed in the classroom. Participation in clubs, English clubs and similar activities also creates a favorable atmosphere for success, which positively affects learning activities.

The development of students' creative abilities. Priorities for improving the education system and the quality of education, which should be put at a new modern level, have been identified. One of the priorities is the support of talented youth, the maximum development of students' intellectually creative abilities.

Technological innovations of the modern world, the gradual transformation of society from a closed to an open, the boom of language industry, the development of intellectual and creative abilities require a completely new attitude to the methodology of teaching a foreign language.

Only using the methodology of developing learning we can talk about the development of intellectual and creative abilities of students. The principle of consciousness and activity is one of the principles of

developmental learning. A student is active when he realizes the purpose of learning and its necessity. The dictionary of foreign words defines reflections such as thinking, self-knowledge and introspection. This is a form of human activity aimed at understanding his own actions. The concept of developing learning involves teaching students how to solve them successfully. The student tries to do something better than others, to be the first and to succeed. Not a teacher, but a student, analyzing, realizes his abilities, draws conclusions himself, and determines the measure of activity and responsibility in his activity. It is necessary to use various methods and techniques of work in order for students to be interested in studying and to increase the motivation for learning a foreign language.

When choosing a particular type of reflection, one should take into account the purpose of the lesson, teaching methods, age and psychological characteristics of students, and can be used at any stage of the lesson. Types and forms of creative work such as tests, mini-essays, essays, letters to friends, design works, abstracts, conferences, supporting abstracts, tables, diagrams, etc. can serve as a logical conclusion to the topic being studied. At the final stage of studying the topic, collective forms of activity are especially advisable when it is necessary to systematize the learned material, determine the degree of formation of skills and abilities, and gain access to practical language skills.

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